
THE IMPACT OF DENTAL ERGONOMIC KNOWLEDGE IN MEDICAL PRACTICE

Eric-Cristian Cirica*Private Dental Practice**Bucharest, Romania***Agnes Katalin Lackner***PhD student; Medical University Wien, University Dental Clinic**Department of Paediatric Dentistry, Vienna, Austria***Andrei Kozma***CSI, Dr.habil. Phd, MMD, DrHC;**„Alessandrescu-Rusescu” National Institute for Mother and Child Health**Member of the Academy of Romanian Scientists**Bucharest, Romania***Abstract**

Dental ergonomics are part of the curriculum of national dental faculties in Romania for decades. The aim of the courses is to accustom students to the principles of dental ergonomics and help them to acquire practical ergonomic skills before performing clinical procedures. Emphasis is put on this subject early in the training of dental students, many disregard these aspects becoming vulnerable to occupational risks.

Neck inclination/rotation, forward bending with loss of cervical and lumbar lordosis and raised arms working in prolonged static isometric/eccentric contraction represent the main risk factors for musculoskeletal disorders (MSD).

In order to obtain the most comprehensive statistics, we have designed three questionnaires. The distribution of these questionnaires was done both physically and online for a period of 2 months (August-September 2024).

The student respondent group gathered 42 responses, all female participants, separated in two large age groups (18-24 and 25-40), studying dental medicine at the "Titu Maiorescu" University (87.5%) or at the "Carol Davila" University of Medicine and Pharmacy (12.5%). A large number of them (62.5%) were working in the medical field during this study.

This leaves us with an estimate of 1 out of 5 residents still not using ergonomic techniques and still suffering painful episodes, while the number of practicing dentists with MSDs is approximately 33%.

Sacrificing a small amount of time to properly position during a long procedure is only going to benefit the practitioner and the patient, the physical stress accumulating during the medical act can heavily impact the result of the treatment.

Keywords: dental ergonomics, mandatory subject, painful episodes, musculoskeletal diseases, residents and practitioners

Introduction

Ergonomics is an interdisciplinary science that promotes health and comfort in the workplace. Although many studies have shown the importance of these principles in dentistry, the majority of clinicians still fail to implement ergonomic guidelines in their dental practices [1, 2]. The dental profession is a physically and mentally demanding job due to the many therapeutical procedures, concentration and mental pressure. Due to the nature of the profession, dentists often sacrifice their posture for the precision of their clinical act. They focus on the treatment procedure and perform long hours without breaks, leaving insufficient time for selfcare.

Neck inclination/rotation, forward bending with loss of cervical and lumbar lordosis and raised arms working in prolonged static isometric/eccentric contraction represent the main risk factors for musculoskeletal disorders (MSDs) [2, 3, 4, 5, 6].

Various international studies assessed MSDs among dental staff by questionnaires and showed generally a high prevalence worldwide. Data collected from a cohort of German *dentists* reported that 86.7% had suffered from spinal problems, particularly in the neck and upper back. Furthermore, a one-year prevalence of MSDs was surveyed among Danish dentists.

The authors reported affliction of the shoulders in 88%, the lower back in 63%, and the neck in 50% (modified Nordic Questionnaire) [7].

The literature shows that despite advances in technology both in the field of dentistry and of dental ergonomics, the development of MSDs in dentists especially in the neck and lower back area is still a problem worldwide. The same situation is found in the case of undergraduate dental students who fail to follow correct posture guidelines during their clinical training. In Romania, there is a majority of dental female students, and they are more prone to develop a variety of chronic musculoskeletal related pain. Apart from MSDs, studies have reported myopia and auditive alterations as negative effects of negligent postural habits.

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Applications of ergonomics in dentistry include a number of different techniques such as adjusting the dental chair, proper placement of instruments and maintaining optimal postures both for clinicians and dental assistants during different clinical procedures. Therefore, in order to prevent the development of more health problems in future and practicing dental clinicians, it is important to make the information easily accessible to students [1, 4].

Materials and methods

In order to obtain the most comprehensive statistics, we have designed three questionnaires. The distribution of these questionnaires was done both physically and online for a period of 2 months (August-September 2024), the physical variant containing an additional question in the first section regarding means of contact (the collection of contact data being necessary to avoid any problem related to the completion of the questionnaires).

The Word and Excel programs from the Office package were used to create and organize the questions and collect the data from them, in parallel with the Google Forms, Google Spreadsheets and Google Drive platforms. According to the rights specified in the

GDPR agreement, both digital and physical data will be stored for 5 years.

The first section contains the GDPR agreement and a set of personal questions, the answers obtained containing the name, gender, age, region and home environment and the environment in which they practice. As the data collected concerned three different target groups, each questionnaire has additional specialized questions in this section. Questionnaires for students and residents contain questions related to the year of study and specialization (for residents only). The questionnaire for dentists does not contain the above mentioned ones but contains a question about the number of years practiced in the field.

The second section covers several topics, such as the application of ergonomic principles during medical procedures, frequency of painful episodes, location of pain, general position of hands, feet and head, and position of the instruments used.

The first table represents the third section of each questionnaire, containing 7 questions related to the importance of properly positioning the limbs and the medical team during the medical act formulated according to the Likert scale, possible answers ranging from "Not important" to "Very important".

Table 1.

Questions from the third section of the questionnaires

For the following questions, the answer is a score ranging from 1 to 5, 1 being the lowest (Not important) and 5 the highest (Very important).						
Nr.	Question	1	2	3	4	5
1.	How important is the position of the feet during the medical act?					
2.	How important is the position of the head during the medical act?					
3.	How important is the position of the back during the medical act?					
4.	How important is the position of the operator light during the medical act?					
5.	How important is the position of the doctor during the medical act?					
6.	How important is the position of the patient during the medical act?					
7.	How important is the position of the dental chair during the medical act?					

The final section is intended to obtain the self-assessment of the respondents' practical and theoretical knowledge of ergonomics and the evaluation of the

quality of dental ergonomic education during academic training (Table 2). Responses are scored from 1 to 10, with 1 being the lowest and 10 being the highest.

Table 2.

Questions from the final section of the questionnaires

For the following questions, the answer is a score ranging from 1 to 10, 1 being the lowest (Insufficient/Minimal) and 10 the highest (Excellent/Comprehensive).											
Nr.	Question	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
1.	How do you rate your knowledge about the theoretical principles of dental ergonomics?										
	How do you rate your knowledge about the practical principles of dental ergonomics?										
3.	How do you evaluate the quality of theoretical ergonomic procedures during academic training?										
4.	How do you evaluate the quality of practical ergonomic procedures during academic training?										

Results

The total number of respondents was 70, 3 of which incorrectly filled in their questionnaire. The final number of correct answers being 67, the percentage of eligible participants is 95.7%. The student respondent

group gathered 42 responses, all female participants, separated in two large age groups (18-24 and 25-40), studying dental medicine at the "Titu Maiorescu" University (87.5%) or at the "Carol Davila" University of Medicine and Pharmacy (12.5%). A large number of

them (62.5%) were working in the medical field during this study. 75% of the participants suffer frequent painful episodes (Figure 1), most of them experiencing

pain located in the neck (50%), chest (12.5%) or the lower back (12.5%).

Figure 1. The frequency of painful episodes (student respondent group)

Significant information is found in the data obtained from the question about the positioning of the arms versus the patient, with most respondents choosing to get as close as possible, the arms are close to the body and the forearms maintain and control the distance between the doctor and the patient as needed

(Figure 2). When choosing the personal optimal distance at which dental instruments are placed, more than half of the responding students are keeping their instruments close to themselves, at no more than 50cm away from their body (Figure 3).

- Arms parallel to the body, forearms bent in proximity of the patient's mouth
- Arms and forearms outstretched towards the patient's mouth
- Arms raised, parallel to the shoulders, forearms bent towards the patient's mouth
- None of the above

Figure 2. Arm positioning during procedures among students (student respondent group)

- More than 1m away from the body
- Between 50cm and 1m away from the body
- No more than 50cm away from the body

Figure 3. Dental instruments' distance from the operator (student respondent group)

No respondent has negatively evaluated the importance of properly positioning their limbs and the medical team, 66% considering their positions as very important, the remaining 34% counting them as quite important.

Responses registered in the final section were extremely varied, with 50% of participants marking their practical and theoretical knowledge of ergonomics below 5, while 37.5% marked the quality of ergonomic education below 3.

When it comes to the group of 16 residents, the academic origin is more diversified, TMU and CDUMP being in equal proportions of 40%, the rest coming from the University of Medicine and Pharmacy in Craiova. 80% of participants reported the lack of pain

in relation to the active use of ergonomic principles. Compared to student respondents, who have completed in equal proportions for each option, residents prioritize only a few operator light targeting methods (Figure 4) and mainly a single choice in the cervical orientation towards the patient (Figure 5).

The rest of the questions in the second section have registered a single answer, those in section 3 receiving scores above 3 (50% for 5, 40% for 4, 10% for 3). Two respondents evaluated their own training and academic knowledge in the field negatively (below the score of 4), 8 assessed theirs neutrally (between 6 and 7), while 6 assessed it positively (between 8 and 10).

Figure 4. Operator light position during the medical act (dental residents group)

Figure 5. Neck position during the medical act (dental residents group)

For the final group, all responses were equally divided, making it difficult to determine the reason for the major change in responses.

Discussions

75% of students, before encountering the optional subject of ergonomics in the final years of study, reported the presence of frequent painful episodes affecting the neck and the lower back. Most likely thanks to constantly learning professionally or academically, statistics change positively when it comes to

respondents who are residents, 80% of them practicing ergonomics and declaring the absence of musculoskeletal complications.

This leaves us with an estimate of 1 out of 5 residents still not using ergonomic techniques and still suffering painful episodes, while the number of practicing dentists with MSDs is approximately 33% (compared to the general number of dentists found in other European studies: - 86.7% German dentists suffering from spinal problems; - 88% shoulder pain afflicted Danish

dentists; - almost 80% of Slovenian dentists affected by MS pain; - 84.6% of Italian dental professionals reporting frequent painful episodes).

Conclusions

Organizing workshops to provide practical advice to students and practitioners in adjusting their position during work and optimizing the workflow, as well as introducing the mandatory subject of dental ergonomics in the final years of the faculty can reduce the frequency of painful episodes that clinicians experience.

A comprehensive course focused on the practical side of the subject could prevent unhealthy habits in their future career and extend the time spent by the specialist practicing dentistry. The active use of ergonomic standards predominantly after the graduation, when students have gathered enough practical knowledge, is essential in minimizing the number of painful episodes.

Sacrificing a small amount of time to properly position during a long procedure is only going to benefit the practitioner and the patient, the physical stress accumulating during the medical act can heavily impact the result of the treatment.

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